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The Role of CEA and CA 19-9 Tumor Markers in Predicting Response to Neoadjuvant Radiochemotherapy in Locally Advanced Rectal Cancer

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Introduction: Locally advanced rectal cancer (LARC) poses significant challenges in oncology, often necessitating multimodal treatment strategies. Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy (nCRT) followed by surgery is the standard approach for LARC management, aimed at improving local control and facilitating sphincter preservation. Tumor markers, such as carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and carbohydrate antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9), have been explored as potential predictors of treatment response and prognosis in various malignancies. This study aimed to evaluate the association between pre- and post-treatment levels of CEA and CA 19-9 and tumor response in LARC patients undergoing nCRT.

Material and Method: We conducted a prospective study including 75 patients with LARC who underwent long-course CRT between June 2020 and January 2022. Treatment involved radiotherapy using volumetric modulated arc therapy-simultaneous integrated boost, along with con-

comitant chemotherapy (5-fluorouracil and leucovorin) administered during the first and fifth weeks of radiotherapy. Tumor response was assessed eight weeks after the completion of nCRT. Patients were categorized as responders (complete clinical response [cCR] and TRG1-2 postoperative categories) or non-responders (TRG3-5) based on the Mandard classification. Levels of CEA and CA 19-9 were measured before treatment initiation and at the completion of therapy.

Results and Discussion: Initial elevated levels of CEA were observed in 41.3% of patients, decreasing to 9.3% post-treatment. Similarly, initial elevated CA 19-9 levels were present in 8% of patients, reducing to 1.3% post-therapy. While no significant association was found between initial CEA levels and treatment response, a significant difference was observed between patients with post-treatment CEA and CA 19-9 levels within reference values compared to those with persistently elevated levels ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that nCRT leads to a significant reduction in CEA and CA 19-9 levels, potentially indicating a favorable treatment response and improved outcomes in LARC patients.

Conclusion: Our study highlights the potential utility of CEA and CA 19-9 as predictive markers for treatment response in LARC patients undergoing neoadjuvant therapy. The significant reduction in tumor marker levels post-treatment suggests a potential role for these markers in assessing therapeutic efficacy and predicting patient outcomes. However, further validation on a larger patient cohort is warranted to confirm these findings and establish the clinical utility of tumor markers in guiding treatment decisions for LARC.

Keywords: locally advanced rectal cancer, neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, hematological toxicities.

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